

Wave-Particle Duality in a Double Slit Teaching Laboratory Experiment

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1 Abstract

This experiment investigated the wave and particle nature of light through interference patterns observed in single-slit and double-slit experiments, using both laser and single photon operation modes. Measured intensity and photon count distribution were then compared with Fraunhofer diffraction and double-slit interference models through curve fitting and parameter extraction.

The observed patterns showed strong internal consistency between single and double slit envelopes, with normalized residue and goodness of fit values indicating close agreement with expected wave forms. However, absolute agreement with theoretical values was limited by systematic uncertainties, with slit geometry and wavelength deviated significantly from manufacturer specifications. The experiment is therefore a reliable as a proof of principle of wave and photon probability reconstruction, rather than precision measurement of optical parameters.

2 Introduction

The nature of light has long been debated as a central topic in optics, electromagnetism and quantum mechanics. In the 17th and 18th centuries, light was described by Newton as the Corpuscular theory of light, and described as small luminous particles emitted by luminous bodies. This model was coherent with reflection and refraction, and therefore dominated early optics theory. However, this model was challenged by the work of Thomas Young, with the double-slit experiment demonstrated the behavior of interference pattern of alternating bright and dark fringes, characteristics only viable through wave like behavior. subsequent works by Fresnel and others described diffraction and interference as an essential property of light. Nonetheless, the emergence of quantum physics in the twentieth century revealed that neither the particle nor wave description model alone is sufficient. Instead, light exhibits wave particle duality and behaves as both a wave and a particle depending on experimental context. We investigate the two contexts within our experiment using a laser and a bulb source.

3 Theory

3.1 Young's double-slit experiment

In 1801, based on the hypothesis from Huygens principle of light as a wave, and that visible light displayed wave like properties such as diffraction, scattering, and constructive and destructive interference. Thomas Young provided evidence for this using the double-slit experiment. By using sunlight diffracted through a small slit as a coherent source, projected upon two narrow parallel slits. Two separate coherent white light sources are created at some distance apart from each other.

Young observed that varying the slit diameter, distance to screen and distance to each other produced the varying patterns of two overlapping patches of light incident on the screen. When he reduced the size of the slits and brought them closer together, the light passing through the slits and onto the screen produced a wider spread of distinct bright and dark spots. This visualised the wave like properties and the term

Figure 1: Wave front passing through single-slit generating the patterns of diffraction by spreading out more when the hole is smaller

interference fringes were coined to describe the bright and dark bands between maxima and minima. Which can only be produced on if light were acting like a wave.

Figure 2: double-slit experiment with a coherent wave source produces an interference pattern on the screen

Within our experiment we attempt to derive both the double-slit widths, and the wavelengths through the following approximated diagram:

Figure 3: theoretical derivation of the wavelength of the light with far field approximation

We can derive the equation of the wavelength and integer multiples for complete constructive interference

$$\Delta pd = m\lambda \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta pd = d \sin \theta \quad (2)$$

$$\therefore d \sin \theta = m\lambda \quad (m \in \mathbb{Z}^+) \quad (3)$$

and at half integer multiples for complete destructive interference

$$\Delta = \left(m + \frac{1}{2}\right) \lambda \quad (4)$$

$$d \sin \theta = \left(m + \frac{1}{2}\right) \lambda \quad (5)$$

We also use far field approximation such that as Intensity from A and B at point p becomes more negligible as $L \gg r_1$ and $L \gg r_2$ are considered. We can use

$$\sin \theta \approx \tan \theta \approx \frac{y}{L} \quad (6)$$

$$y_m = \frac{m\lambda L}{d} \quad (7)$$

However, several theoretical assumptions were made in this experiment, including the simultaneous nature of waves emitted at the same time to reach the pattern, and the phase shift of light at bending of the slits edge being neglected. This assumption will need to be revised and recalibrated for a precise visualisation of probability amplitudes for a quantum mechanics caricature.

3.2 single-slit experiment

light passing through a single narrow slit undergoes diffraction and produces a intensity distribution described by a wide and bright central maximum, and diminishing sides. In our experiment, we initialise the laser and light bulb source through this slit.

Figure 4: single-slit experiment showcases the interference pattern over a spread out interval

In addition, we measure the interference pattern for the case when one of the double-slits is blocked. This allows us to verify that the wave diffracts with itself.

$$\Delta pd = m\lambda \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta pd = a \sin \theta \quad (9)$$

$$(10)$$

$$a \sin \theta = m\lambda \quad (m = \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots) \quad (11)$$

We also note that as the slit itself is varied, our diffraction angle will be inversely varied also, as smaller slit width will result in a larger diffraction angle as waves become more spread out.

3.3 Quantum Nature of double-slit experiment

However, the classical interpretation of Young's double-slit experiment was extended into the quantum regime through electron interference experiments, such as those conducted at the CNR-LAMEL laboratory in 1976. In this experiment, an electron beam generated from a cold field emission source was split within an electron microscope using an electrostatic bi-prism. this produced two light paths similar to a double-slit.

Remarkably, when the beam intensity was reduced such that electrons passed through the slits one at a time, the accumulation of individual detection events over time formed the same interference fringe pattern

observed in the double-slit experiment. This indicates that interference persists even when detection occurs as discrete events.

This result implies that each electron exhibits wave-like behavior described by a probability amplitude, while detection itself localized and makes the measurement discrete. As such, the paths of the individualized photon is incompatible with the measurement of the interference pattern.

The observed interference pattern therefore reflects the probability distribution of each measurement. This experimentally verifies the thought experiment described by Feynman, in which individual particles interfere with themselves [?, Vol. I, Ch. 37].

In our experiment, we used a photomultiplier tube to detect and localize the arrival of each photon. Through the scanning of the interference pattern, we verify the statistical distribution of photon arrivals also form the accumulation of the interference fringe pattern observed in the double-slit experiment.

Figure 5: electron interference experiments which supports the individualize particles characteristics of light

3.4 Photoelectric effect

In 1905, photoelectric effect experiment provided light through a particle view. Monochromatic light of a certain frequency was incident upon a metal zinc surface within a vacuum tube. At above a certain frequency $f_{threshold}$, electrons were instantaneously (within $1ns$) emitted from the zinc plating and collected at the anode and measured as photocurrent through an ammeter, and later its maximum kinetic energy is determined.

$$E = hf \tag{12}$$

$$K_{max} = hf - \phi \tag{13}$$

where ϕ is work function of the metal.

It was observed that this kinetic energy is dependent upon the frequency of the incident light and the work function of the metal, and not on the intensity of the light. Increasing the intensity of the light only increases the number of electrons but not their maximum kinetic energy.

This linear dependence contradict classical theory of waves, which predicts wave energy should depend on intensity. Einstein therefore proposed that light is consisted of discrete packets (photons), each photon has energy proportional to its frequency.

Figure 6: The photoelectric effect shows that light has momentum and can be considered as particles

3.5 Wave Particle Duality

The combination of interference phenomena and discrete energy transfer reveals that light cannot be described purely as either a wave or a particle. Instead, it exhibits wave-particle duality, where its propagation is governed by wave-like behaviour, while its interaction with matter occurs in discrete localised events.

3.6 Experimental aim

In this experiment, we consider light as both a continuous source, as well as a quantized source. we expected to see a interference pattern when the laser source passes through both slits, and we expect to observe a similar interference pattern when quantised bulb source passes through both slits. We also expect to see

diffraction pattern of the single-slit laser experiment. Additionally, we infer that no light will pass through when both slits are closed.

4 Experimental Setup

The experiment was conducted using a *two-slit interference apparatus* (TWS-2A), consisting of an enclosed optical bench of approximately 1m in length. The setup contains a controllable laser and light source, single and double-slit systems, and detection modules to investigate interference patterns in both classical and single-photon regimes.

At the left hand side of the bench, a light source panel provides selectable light sources: a coherent laser and a low intensity monochromatic light bulb. The laser is used for quantitative alignment and visual measurements, while the bulb source ($\lambda \approx 541\text{--}551\text{ nm}$) enables single photon detection and measurement. Light from this source first passes through a the initial single-slit acts as a spatial filter, improving transverse coherence of the source and ensuring well-defined interference fringes at the double-slit ensemble.

A movable slit blocker controlled by the micrometer allows selective transmission through 1 or 2 slits. At the right hand side of the bench, a detector slit is mounted on a translational mount in line with the interference pattern, and allows detection system to laterally scan and select portions of the interference pattern.

The fringe spacing is governed by the relation $\Delta x = \frac{\lambda L}{d}$, where L is the distance to the detector and d is the slit separation, providing a direct link between the experimental geometry and observed pattern.

Two detection devices are utilised

- A **photodiode**, which converts incident light intensity into a voltage signal for quantitative measurements using a digital multimeter.
- A **photomultiplier tube (PMT)**, which detects individual photon events in single-photon mode. The PMT output is connected to a pulse counter and oscilloscope to measure photon rates.

In photo-diode mode, the continuous intensity is measured $I(x)$, while in single photon mode the PMT records discrete photon counts, whose spatial distribution and probability envelope reproduces a similar interference pattern over time.

All measurements are performed with the apparatus enclosed to eliminate ambient light interference. Adjustable micrometer dials are used to precisely control the positions of the single-slit, double-slit blocker, and detector slit. A white card is occasionally inserted into the optical path to visually confirm beam alignment.

The entire optical experiment setup is enclosed by a removable cover during all operations. This eliminates ambient lighting and allows more accurate detection. Adjustable micrometer dials are used to control the both the double-slit blockers and the detector slit position. A white paper card is handled to visualize the alignment of the laser during initial experiment setup, this allows precise and verifiable experimental data to be produced by the quantitative and single photon sources.

The block diagram of the full setup is given in the experiment manual

Figure 7: Setup of experiment apparatus (Phys2111 lab manual, 2026)

A list of source, detector and adjoining slits and distances are listed in the table below

Parameter	Value
single-slit width	0.085 mm
single-slit height	1 cm
double-slit width	0.085 mm
Slit separation	0.457 mm
Distance (single \rightarrow double-slit)	30 cm
Distance (double-slit \rightarrow detector)	49.5 cm
Wavelength (bulb source)	541–551 nm

5 Methodology

The experiment was conducted in two stages: classical wave interference measurement using a laser source followed by a single-photon detection using a light bulb emitting at (10Hz) and a photomultiplier tube (PMT).

5.1 Initial Setup and Alignment

The optical bench was assembled according to the laboratory manual. All components, including the slit and detector ensemble were verified to be securely mounted. All dials, controls and adjustments were made in accordance to the setup. An external multimeter was connected and calibrated and the micrometer controls for the slit blocker and detector were tested to ensure smooth and precise operation and calibrated also.

A coherent laser source was used for alignment. The beam was adjusted so that the central maximum was incident upon the paper target. Which was placed in front of the detector slit to ensuring proper alignment of both lateral and vertical axis through the single-slit, double-slit and detector slit.

The slit blocker micrometer was calibrated by identifying the positions corresponding to the following configurations:

- Both slits blocked
- Near slit open only
- Both slits open
- Far slit open only

5.2 Wave Interference Measurement

With both slits open, the detector slit was translated laterally across a full left side of the interference pattern using the micrometer. At each position, the light intensity was measured using a photodiode connected to a digital multimeter. Measurements were recorded at regular spatial intervals of (0.05mm, 0.2mm, 0.5mm) to capture the full fringe distribution, smaller interval were used in maxima and minima which were of particular interest.

The procedure was repeated for single-slit configurations by blocking the near slit. Care was taken to maintain consistent step sizes and prevent any measurement error such as parallax or alignment error during both trials.

5.3 Single-Photon Measurement

The laser source was removed, and the low-intensity light bulb was activated to level 8. The apparatus enclosure was secured to eliminate ambient light. As well as the detection PMT were setup in accordance with the manual to include both a correct level 6 threshold, the counting time interval of 1 seconds was utilised to meaningfully capture a large enough deviation across the sweep.

The detector slit was again translated across the expected interference region, and 3 photon counts were recorded as at each interval. This process was repeated under identical geometric conditions to those used in the classical measurements.

5.4 Verification and Consistency

We checked the results with official data to ensure accuracy. This ensured that alignment was correct throughout all 3 sweeps. To minimize backlash and measurement error, care was taken to pause to allow each measurement to stabilise, preliminary sweeps were used to provide an initial position to ensure the efficient capture of meaningful data during each sweep.

6 Data and Results

6.1 Raw data

After conducting standard data analysis through raw extraction, smoothing, model fitting, and comparison of extracted values. We yield a value of $245 \pm 1.72nm$ for single-slit and $331 \pm 3.71nm$ for double-slit using laser source and $285.33 \pm 3.71nm$ as an approximation from the single photon operating mode.

This indicates that interference envelope from the the wave and particle agrees with the wavelength to slit width ratio.

This result is significant with our hypothesis and verifies Young's double-slit experiment and the wave particle duality of light.

Basic data validation was performed by removing rows containing missing values or NaN entries. After cleaning, we obtained 4 initial envelopes called singlewave, singlewave2, doublewave and doublepart.

Singlewave (outer scan) and Singlewave (inner scan).

Figure 8: Raw diffraction patterns measured for single-slit laser.

doublewave:

doublepart:

Based on the raw data from above, we extracted the following tableued maximas and minimas for each pattern:

6.2 Fitted data

We understand that the theoretical intensity distribution for Fraunhofer diffraction from a single-slit is

Figure 9: Raw diffraction patterns measured for single-slit laser.

Figure 10: Raw diffraction patterns measured for single-slit laser.

$$I(\theta) = I_0 \left(\frac{\sin \beta}{\beta} \right)^2,$$

a is the slit width and λ is the wavelength of the light.

For small diffraction angles, the detector position x is related to the angle by

$$\theta \approx \frac{x}{L},$$

Table 1: Measured Positions of Diffraction Features

Measurement	Position (mm)
single-slit (Wave)	
Peak → first minima (single-slit)	2.9000
double-slit (Wave)	
First minima	1.8000
Second minima	1.1000
Third minima	0.3500
double-slit (Particle)	
First minima	1.6000
Second minima	0.9500
Third minima	0.3500

where L is the distance between the slit and the detector. Substituting this relation gives an intensity profile proportional to

$$I(x) = A \operatorname{sinc}^2[B(x - x_0)],$$

where A is the peak intensity, x_0 is the central peak position, and B is a parameter related to the slit width. Similarly, we know that for double-slit interference pattern is given by The interference pattern is given by the product of the single-slit diffraction *envelope* and the interference fringes produced by the two coherent sources and is

$$I(\theta) = I_0 \cos^2 \alpha \left(\frac{\sin \beta}{\beta} \right)^2 \quad (14)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi d \sin \theta}{\lambda} \quad (15)$$

$$\beta = \frac{\pi a \sin \theta}{\lambda} \quad (16)$$

Here:

- d is the separation between the slits,
- a is the width of each slit,
- λ is the wavelength of the light.

Using the small-angle approximation, the intensity distribution on the detector becomes

$$I(x) = A \cos^2[C(x - x_0)] \operatorname{sinc}^2[B(x - x_0)] \quad (17)$$

where

$$B = \frac{\pi a}{\lambda L} \quad (18)$$

$$C = \frac{\pi d}{\lambda L} \quad (19)$$

and:

- A is the peak intensity at $x = x_0$,
- x_0 is the central maximum position,

- L is the distance from the slits to the detector,
- $\text{sinc}(u) = \frac{\sin u}{u}$.

Thus, we plot these theoretical relations in our refined datasets.

Figure 11: Raw diffraction patterns measured for single-slit laser.

Figure 12: Raw diffraction patterns measured for double-slit laser.

Based on the fits from above, we also extracted these parameterized values:

Figure 13: Raw detection patterns measured for double-slit PMT.

7 Data Processing

To enable direct comparison between datasets, the measured signals were centered at the central maximum with value of $x = 0$, and the symmetry of the interference patterns was utilized and only the significant half of each envelope were fitted to improve stability and reduce noise.

For the single-slit pattern, both the outer and inner scans were combined to increase the number of data points across the diffraction envelope. As the two scans align reasonably well, it is justified to model them using a single sinc^2 relation.

For the double-slit photon dataset, each data point was obtained by averaging three 1-second photon count measurements from the photomultiplier tube (PMT), this allowed the reduction of errors through averaging at each datapoint.

To minimize edge-effects and instability in the fitting procedure, data points far from the central maximum particularly beyond the first minima and third maxima were excluded. This ensures that the fitting focuses on the region where the theoretical model is most valid.

As observed, all the minima values for both methods are aligned with an error of approximately < 0.05 . This supports the curve fitting. We explore the curves using RMSE, chi squared and linear fit below.

8 Trend analysis

8.1 (A) Fit Quality

The single-slit model yielded an RMSE of 0.0018, indicating excellent agreement between the sinc^2 model and the measured data. The double-slit wave fit showed moderate agreement (RMSE ≈ 0.02). This shows the model for the single-slit diffraction were excellent and our wave source slit were based upon reliable data. The single-photon dataset exhibited a larger RMSE (≈ 19.4). However, this is primarily due to the larger scale of the measured photon counts (on the order of 10^3). Upon normalisation, the RMSE reduces to approximately 0.02. This indicates a comparable level of agreement to the double-slit wave data.

Table 2: Measured Maxima and Minima for single-slit, double-slit, and Single Photon Data

Case	Feature	Position x	Intensity y
single-slit	Maximum	4.1342	0.0322
	Minimum	2.8879	5.6344×10^{-4}
double-slit	Maximum 1	1.4111	1.3650
	Maximum 2	0.7009	2.5865
	Minimum 1	1.8112	0.0796
	Minimum 2	1.0810	0.0796
	Minimum 3	0.3513	0.0796
Single Photon	Maximum 1	1.2242	5.516×10^2
	Maximum 2	0.6263	9.251×10^2
	Maximum 3	0.0249	1.0963×10^3
	Minimum 1	1.5592	134.8793
	Minimum 2	0.9455	134.8794
	Minimum 3	0.3319	134.8797

Figure 14: Curve fitting residuals plot for all 3 setups.

8.2 (B) Parameter Consistency

Using the equations listed above, we obtain the slit a/λ from the single-slit and d/λ from the double-slit envelopes. We report they are consistent and do support expected relation between maxima and minima. The double-slit wave dataset yielded $d/\lambda \approx 1.38$, in agreement with both linear regression and nonlinear fitting methods. This consistency indicates a reliable extraction of fringe spacing.

8.3 (C) Linear fit Comparison

The extracted values of a/λ from both the single-slit and double-slit envelope fits were highly consistent (0.3455 vs 0.3415), validating the theoretical relationship between diffraction and interference. Linear regression of the minima positions yielded $d/\lambda \approx 1.38$, which is consistent with values obtained from nonlinear curve fitting. This agreement shows that both fitting approaches reliably capture the fringe spacing.

Linear regression of the minima positions for the particle dataset yielded a larger value of $d/\lambda = 1.6016$.

Table 3: Goodness of Fit Metrics

Case	RMSE	χ^2
single-slit	0.0018	1.035
Double Wave	0.0199	1.111
Double Part	19.3954	1.129

Table 4: Dimensionless Ratios

Source	Value
single-slit (a/λ)	345.54
double-slit Envelope (a/λ)	341.54
double-slit Fringes (d/λ)	1371.21

This deviation is likely due to increased statistical fluctuations in photon count. However it is sufficiently accurate in demonstrating a similarity to wave like model under lower signal-to-noise conditions with only 3 samples per datapoint.

Figure 15: Linear fit for dimensionless ratio of aperture / wavelength .

8.4 (D) Linear fit Confidence

The CI of the linear fit are generally consistent across trials, with narrow confidence intervals indicating stable estimation. Trials 1 and 2 exhibit tight bounds on parameter B , suggesting high precision. Trial 3 shows a wider confidence interval, indicating a slight reduction in confidence of the fit. This is as expected due to the increased signal to noise due to low sample size.

8.5 (E) Model based Interpretation

The agreement between wave-based models and experimental data does indicate the wave nature of light. Additionally, the similarity of the interference pattern in the photon measurement envelop shows that in-

Table 5: Linear Fit Parameters for double-slit Wave Minima

Parameter	Value
Slope m (mm/order)	0.72
Intercept b (mm)	-0.36
d/λ	1380.69

Table 6: Linear Fit Parameters for double-slit Particle Minima

Parameter	Value
Slope m (mm/order)	0.62
Intercept b (mm)	-0.28
d/λ	1601.60

terference is not dependent on classical wave intensity, but arises from the probabilistic nature of photon detection. This further supports of the wave and particle nature of light

8.6 double-slit Comparative Study

Based on the fitted parameters and values direct extracted from the raw plot, a comparative study was performed across the measured single-slit, double-slit (wave), and double-slit photon datasets and with manufacturer specifications.

Using these manufacture values, the theoretical ratios are

$$\frac{a}{\lambda} \approx \frac{9.0 \times 10^{-5}}{5.46 \times 10^{-7}} \approx 165, \quad \frac{d}{\lambda} \approx \frac{4.5 \times 10^{-4}}{5.46 \times 10^{-7}} \approx 824.$$

When compared to experimental values from above, we have approximately an order of 2x to the datasheet values, this suggests that our experimental values may have been scaled. If this were so, the scaling for all interference envelopes were around 1.8- 2 times.

Despite this, strong internal consistency is observed. The values of a/λ obtained from the single-slit and double-slit envelope fits are in agreement, and the values of d/λ derived from wave-based methods are consistent across both linear and nonlinear fitting approaches.

The combined double-slit model,

$$I(x) = A \cos^2[B(x - x_0)] \operatorname{sinc}^2[C(x - x_0)],$$

provided consistent parameter estimates for both wave and particle datasets. While the single-photon data exhibits larger fluctuations due to the Poisson nature of photon detection, the underlying interference structure remains clearly observable.

Overall, the sinc^2 envelope and \cos^2 modulation provide a robust basis for modelling diffraction and interference patterns. The agreement between datasets reinforces the reliability of the experimental procedure and supports the wave-based description of light.

9 Uncertainty

Uncertainty in this experiment arises from both statistical (Type A) and systematic (Type B) contributions.

9.1 Type A Uncertainty (Statistical)

Type A uncertainty arises due to the fluctuations in the measurement of signal, sources of error within the experiment.

However, as we only have 1 measurement at each data point along each envelope. it is better for us to only assess the type A uncertainty theoretically in the photon-counting regime. With the photomultiplier tube (PMT) measurements follow Poisson statistics, with uncertainty given by Poisson distribution

Table 7: Curve Fit Parameters

Trial	Parameter	Value
Trial 1	C	1.0845
	x_0	-0.0094
	95% CI (B)	[1.0789, 1.0900]
Trial 2	A	3.0741
	B	4.3035
	C	1.0719
	D	0.0796
	x_0	0.0139
	95% CI (B)	[4.2923, 4.3148]
Trial 3	A	3.0741
	B	4.3035
	C	1.0719
	D	0.0796
	x_0	0.0139
	95% CI (B)	[5.0762, 5.1618]

Table 8: Manufacturer Specifications

Component	Specification
Interference Filter	546 ± 5 nm
Slit Width (a)	0.09 mm
Slit Separation (d)	0.45 mm
Optical Path Length (L)	≈ 1.0 m

$$\sigma = \sqrt{N}$$

$$\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}} < 0.01$$

where N is the photon count. however, due to high photon count per second and averaging at data points, Poisson noise is reduced to <0.01 and is not significant.

9.2 Type B Uncertainty (Systematic)

Type B uncertainty arises from limitations in the measurement system. The significant sources and their estimated standard uncertainties are:

- **Micrometer resolution:**

The detector position was measured using a micrometer with resolution ± 0.01 mm, thus giving a standard uncertainty

$$u_x = \frac{0.01}{\sqrt{12}} \approx 2.89 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm.}$$

- **Wavelength spread (interference filter):**

The filter has a bandwidth of 10 nm (FWHM), corresponding to a uncertainty

$$u_\lambda = \frac{10}{2\sqrt{2 \ln 2}} \approx 4.25 \text{ nm.}$$

- **Slit dimensions:** The slit width (0.09 mm) and separation (0.35–0.45 mm) are subject to manufacturing tolerances, at ± 0.01 mm,

$$u_d = u_a = \frac{0.01}{\sqrt{3}} \approx 5.77 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm.}$$

- **Optical path length:** The total length of light path ($1m$) was measured with a ruler of resolution ± 1 mm, giving

$$u_L = \frac{1}{\sqrt{12}} \approx 0.29 \text{ mm.}$$

- **Alignment errors:** Misalignment of the laser, optical rail and detector introduces an estimated positional uncertainty of

$$u_{\text{align}} \approx 0.02 \text{ mm.}$$

- **Electronics and detector:** The photo detector provides a voltage which is amplified and sent to the digital multimeter, we assume the combined resultant voltage readout has a resolution of approx.

$$\delta V \approx \pm 0.01 \text{ V.}$$

The combined positional uncertainty of each ratio a/λ and d/λ , is therefore.

$$u_{\text{pos}} = R \sqrt{\left(\frac{u_L}{L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_y}{y}\right)^2}.$$

Using $u_L = 0.29$ mm and the combined positional uncertainty $u_y = \sqrt{u_x^2 + u_{\text{align}}^2} \approx 0.0202$ mm, we obtain for the single-slit ratio

$$\frac{a}{\lambda} = 345.54 \pm 2.42$$

which corresponds to a relative uncertainty of 0.70%.

For the double-slit wave dataset,

$$\frac{d}{\lambda} = 1380.69 \pm 15.4$$

corresponding to a relative uncertainty of 1.12%.

For the single-photon double-slit dataset,

$$\frac{d}{\lambda} = 1601.60 \pm 20.8$$

corresponding to a relative uncertainty of 1.30%.

And for our experiment, we can substituting all significant uncertainty values to measure our overall instrumental system uncertainty budget formed by combining all identified sources in quadrature.

To estimate an overall uncertainty budget for the entire experiment, all identified independent uncertainty contributions were combined in quadrature as relative uncertainties:

$$u_{\text{relative}} = \sqrt{u_{\text{Poisson}}^2 + \left(\frac{u_x}{y}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_a}{a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_d}{d}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_\lambda}{\lambda}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_L}{L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_V}{V}\right)^2}.$$

Substituting the experimental values gave

$$u_{\text{exp,rel}} \approx 0.0667,$$

corresponding to an overall experimental uncertainty of approximately

$$\pm 6.7\% \quad (1\sigma).$$

The most dominant sources of uncertainty arises from alignment error, reading error and wavelength spread. Which has the greatest impact on the fringe spacing and derived slit width and wavelength parameters. In this way, bias is introduced in the results.

Monte Carlo propagation To quantify and simulate the effects of all measurement uncertainties, a Monte Carlo simulation with 10^4 trials was performed using the

$$\pm 6.7\% \quad (1\sigma).$$

result from 1σ . Random perturbations mostly from Type B uncertainty concerned with instrumental noise (position, sampling interval, and measurement noise) were applied to the data. The resulting distribution of fitted parameters represents the combined uncertainty of the double-slit ensemble, incorporating both statistical fluctuations and instrumental limitations on all 3 setups.

Figure 16: Monte Carlo distribution for lambda using the overall relative experimental setup uncertainty.

10 Discussion

Throughout our experiment, we have generated strong evidence which supports the duality of light, and the probabilistic nature of single photon measurement. The observed interference pattern in both classical and quantum regimes are consistent with theory from above. and reinforce the principle of wave particle duality.

The experimental setup was sufficiently valid. Some measures were taken to approximate the external noise and interference sources. The use of rigorous uncertainty and fits provides strong evidence for a valid experimental analysis. Therefore, while the experiment itself is valid for the purpose of demonstration of physical principles. Improvements in calibration and instrumentation are desirable for comparison with theoretical values.

10.1 Accuracy

The experiment was moderately accurate, as measurement scale, calibration, device and light sources discrepancy were all considered and observed between measured values and that of theoretical derivations.

Thus, there is strong evidence to suggest the presence of a systematic scaling error, likely arising from misinterpretation of instrument calibration (e.g. dial-to-distance conversion), incorrect initial values setup or

lab manual, or transcription errors. As this deviation was consistent across multiple datasets, it is unlikely to be random and instead reflects a systematic bias in our measured envelopes..

10.2 Precision

Although the experiment was conducted in a professional student lab environment, using equipment provided such as

detector aperture.

source aperture.

optical benches

optical bench ruler

measurement electronics

Provides a sufficiently strong evidence to verify the wave nature and measurements of the double-slit experiment, As we noted that internally our experimental ratios for slits and wavelength were consistent across both single and double-slit setups.

10.3 Validity

Despite limitations in absolute accuracy, the experiment demonstrated good internal coherence. Measurements across both single and double-slit configurations were consistent, and key ratios (such as fringe spacing and relative peak widths) are reproducible given the same conditions.

Use of optical bench, controlled alignment and well documented measurement procedures ensured that relative trends were reliable. This allows meaningful comparison between envelopes, even as absolute values deviated strongly from theoretical expectations

11 Conclusion

The double-slit experiment investigated the wave and particle behaviour of light using interference and diffraction measurement across laser and a light bulb. We observed the interference pattern do align with the appropriate fitting of the single-slit sinc^2 and double-slit $\text{sinc}^2\cos^2$ model. Providing strong evidence for the wave nature of light . Further, the extracted pattern from single photon double-slit measurements also aligned and contributed strongly to the replication of quantum probability distribution with that of classical interference pattern.

Although agreement with theoretical values was limited, the analysis demonstrated sufficient internal consistency and for this reason. If evaluated on the ability to indicate and reproduce the expected trend behavior than that of pedagogical accuracy, we have successfully achieved its aim by exploring the underlying nature of light through its properties of diffraction and interference.

Further improvements, including better calibration, verified slit specifications, and higher-precision optical components, would be required to obtain closer quantitative agreement with accepted values.

A Appendix A: Bibliography and Resources

MATLAB and Code Resources

The data processing, curve fitting, and analysis were performed using MATLAB. The following documentation was used:

- MathWorks, *MATLAB Documentation*. Available at: <https://www.mathworks.com/help/matlab/>
- Curve fitting functions: <https://www.mathworks.com/help/curvefit/fit.html>
- Confidence intervals: <https://www.mathworks.com/help/curvefit/cfit.confint.html>
- Sinc function: <https://www.mathworks.com/help/signal/ref/sinc.html>
- Linear fitting: <https://www.mathworks.com/help/stats/fitlm.html>

Theoretical References

Textbook references

- D. J. Griffiths, *Introduction to Electrodynamics*, 4th ed., Pearson, 2013.
- Hecht, E., *Optics*, 4th ed., Addison-Wesley, 2002.

Supplementary references:

- Evident Scientific, *Thomas Young's double-slit Experiment*. Available at: <https://evidentscientific.com/en/microscope-resource/tutorials/doubleslitwavefronts>
- Physics Stack Exchange, *A question about photoelectric effect (graph)*. Available at: <https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/531053/a-question-about-photoelectric-effect-graph>
- Energy Wave Theory, *double-slit Experiment*. Available at: <https://energywavetheory.com/explanations/double-slit-experiment/>
- Physics Stack Exchange, *In the double-slit Experiment, what type of wave are we talking about?*. Available at: <https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/576767/in-the-double-slit-experiment-what-type->

The format and template itself is a variation of Overleaf. (n.d.). *NTNU laboratory report in physics*. Overleaf. <https://www.overleaf.com/latex/templates/ntnu-laboratory-report-in-physics/zrkxstqtpdpv>

And lastly, all AI syntax assistance usage are from:

OpenAI, 2026. *ChatGPT (GPT-5.3)* [Large language model]. <https://chat.openai.com/>
Google, 2026. *Gemini* [Large language model]. <https://gemini.google.com/>

All experimental measurements, analysis decisions, interpretations, and final responsibility for the work remain with the author.

A Appendix B: Lab Notes

Prework 1:

1a. * we know that the path difference between 2 slits in a double slit experiment corresponds to complete constructive interference when they equate to an integer multiple of the source wavelength.

$$\Delta p.d = m\lambda$$

using figure 1a:

$$\Delta p.d = d \sin \theta \text{ for small angle approximation of } \theta < 15^\circ$$

$$\text{so we get: } d \sin \theta = m\lambda \quad m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$$

Similarly we understand complete destructive interference occurs when p.d equate half integer multiples of source wavelength.

$$\Delta p.d = (m + \frac{1}{2}) \lambda$$

$$d \sin \theta = (m + \frac{1}{2}) \lambda \quad m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$$

1b * if we show we. θ as small $\sin \theta = \tan \theta = \frac{y}{L}$

we get $y = \sin \theta L$ $y = \frac{m\lambda L}{d}$ y is distance between bright spots
this denotes y increases when λ, L increases and decreases when d increased.

Analysis: find min and max:

we. Savitzky Golay filter:

$$\text{let } y = a_0 + a_1 x + a_2 x^2 + \dots + a_p x^p.$$

or minimize $\sum w^2$ of point and polynomial at y_i each value.

as window size \downarrow smaller, high polynomial / more coefficients are used.

So. as window size \downarrow polynomial degree \uparrow .

step 2 \rightarrow localized polynomial.

\rightarrow then find maxima via $\frac{dy}{dx} = 0$. for global max / mins.

$$y = \frac{m\lambda L}{d} \quad \frac{dy}{d} = \frac{y}{mL} \quad \text{so } \frac{dy}{d} \approx \frac{y}{mL}$$

$$d\theta = m\lambda \quad \text{find ratios.}$$

A Appendix C: Matlab code

<https://github.com/Skippertheev/Experiment-data-analysis/blob/a94c76ea6c15e5fa529f66f6be83fe71aeb9368f5/doubleslit.m>